

**EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE ON THE INFLUENCE OF
EXPERIENTIAL INSTRUCTIONAL DESIGN LEARNING
ACTIVITIES ON BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS'
E-BUSINESS COMPETENCY DEVELOPMENT**

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Abstract:

This study examined the influence of experiential instructional design learning activities proposed by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) on business education students' electronic business (e-business) competencies development in Colleges of Education in Rivers State. To achieve the main purpose of the study, two specific purposes, two research questions and one hypothesis were posed. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to obtain data on participants' self-evaluation. The population of the study was made up of 22 part-time Business education NCE I students from Federal College of Education (Tech.), Omoku during the 2018/2019 academic session. A research designed questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha to obtain a reliability index of 0.72. Data collected for the study were analysed using mean and simple linear regression. The findings show that the students highly develop e-business competencies evaluated. The result of test of hypothesis showed that experiential instructional design learning activities has significant influence on business education students' development of e-business competencies. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others business educators who want to bridge the gap should adopt experiential instructional design.

Keywords: instructional design, competency development, e-business, learning activities, business education

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1. Introduction

This era of technology integration in business operations has made it necessary for Business education graduates to be trained on how to utilize technological offerings in different aspects of business. It is in recognition of this necessity, that National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2012) included computer related topics in most aspects of Business education courses such as: marketing (e-commerce, e-marketing and e-business), Information and Communication Technology (ICT)/Computer application (such as: Microsoft word, Excel spreadsheet application, computer data analysis application), and office practice (e-payments). Hence, Business education students are expected to learn these technological application areas in business in order to develop the requisite competencies to function effectively in today's technological driven business world.

To assist Business education graduates from Colleges of Education develop e-business competencies, there is need to shift from the traditional instructional designs that favour theoretical knowledge competence acquisition to instructional designs that guarantees both theoretical knowledge competence acquisition and skills and attitude related competencies development. Supporting this, Ozuruoke and Abdulkarim (2016) noted that with the advancement of technology and its integration in doing businesses, traditional methods of instruction such as: lecturer and demonstration methods alone cannot be utilized to assist Business education students develop e-business competencies. This is due to the fact that competency as described by Ebuka (2000) and Ordu (2016) is the ability to do something well when assessed based on predetermined standards and this can only be acquired through experience and training. Judy and Chris in James (2014) described competency as combination of knowledge, attitudes, values and skills required to perform tasks in determined situations. In same vein, Mitchelmore and Rowley (2010) also described e-business competencies as generic and specific knowledge, skills and attitudes needed to create, sustain and grow business ventures successfully. Oborah (2014) noted that Business students need to develop fundamental e-commerce competencies in order to function effectively and efficiently in the entry-level employment in the e-commerce industry. Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) also pointed out that electronic business competencies are knowledge, attitude and skills required to effectively and efficiently carry on electronic business operations such as e-commerce, e-marketing, and e-payment. Therefore, it is paramount to utilize instructional designs that would expose business education students to learning experiences capable of developing their e-business competencies for effective and efficient operations in the business world.

There are many instructional designs that can be adopted and utilized by Business educators to assist their students develop e-business competences related to e-related topics in Business education courses. According to Gayla (2015), these instructional designs can be classified as: interactive, experiential or independent. Gray, Stein, Osborne, and Aitken (2013) also opined that for the purpose of assisting learners to acquire knowledge, develop skills and attitude in any course, instructional designs

that support strategies that immersed students in learning activities such as: indirect, interactive or experiential should be utilized. In promoting the use of such instructional designs that support the immersion of students in the learning process, Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) advocated for the use of experiential instructional design to equip Business education students with e-business competencies. Their proposed design was based on Kolb's experiential learning theory (1984) which states that knowledge is created through the transformation of experience(s). The authors outlined the expected learning outcomes and learning activities that Business education students should undertake based on experiential instructional design in order to develop e-business competencies at the NCE level. Their proposed instructional design is detailed as follows:

Table 1: Experiential Instructional Design for e-business Competencies Development

Learning objectives:	<p>At the end of the learning activities, students should be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Define what online stores do. ii. State the technologies needed for navigating any online store. iii. State the knowledge needed for buying from online store. iv. State the skills needed for navigating from one online store to another. v. Explain the procedures of buying from an online store. vi. Purchase from an online store item(s) not worth more than N2,000. vii. Make payment using any e-payment platform e.g. mobile banking, inter-switch or ATM viii. Explain the logistics associated with buying online. ix. Create e-marketing advert for reselling what they bought from online store. x. Market product using social media platform e.g. Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram. xi. State the challenges associated with buying and selling using electronic digital technology.
Learning activities:	<p>For the purpose of grasping the knowledge students would be required to carry out the following learning activities in a team of five:</p> <p>Concrete Experience (CE): Each member of the group would:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Download three online stores' application on his/her smart phones e.g. Jumia, Konga and Kaymu or visit the websites of the three online stores. ii. Navigate through each of the online store's application and define what they offer to the public. iii. Purchase an educational item(s) not more than N2,000 from any of the online stores after comparing the price, quality and ease of delivery. iv. Design an e-marketing advert to sell the educational item(s) to colleagues at affordable prices. v. Collect the data of request for the items sent in by your colleagues. vi. Sell to Colleagues who meets the conditions of sales ensuring they make payment directly using e-payment platform. <p>Abstract Conceptualization (AC): Each member of the group would:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Analyse and discuss how he downloaded three online stores' application on his/her smart phones e.g. Jumia, Konga and Kaymu or Visit the websites of the three online stores. ii. Discuss how to navigate through each of the online store's application

- and define what they offer to the public.
- iii. Discuss the procedures followed in purchasing an educational item(s) not more than N2,000 from any of the online stores after comparing the price, quality and ease of delivery.
- iv. Discuss and analyse his/her design of e-marketing advert to sell the educational item purchased to colleagues at affordable price.
- v. Discuss how to collect the data of request for the items sent in by colleagues for purchase.
- vi. Discuss how the items were sold and how payment was received from colleagues.

Reflective Observation (RO): Each member of the group would:

- i. Observe other members talking and reflect on how he/she downloaded three online stores' application on his/her smart phones e.g. Jumia, Konga and Kaymu or visit the websites of the three online stores.
- ii. Observe other members talking and reflect on how he/she navigates through each of the online store's application and define what they offer to the public.
- iii. Observe other members talking and reflect on the procedures he/she followed in purchasing an educational item(s) not more than N2,000 from any of the online stores after comparing the price, quality and ease of delivery.
- iv. Observe other members talking and reflect on how he/she designed e-marketing advert to sell the educational item he purchased to colleagues at affordable prices.
- v. Observe member talking and reflect on how he/she collected the data of request for the items sent in by colleagues for purchase.
- vi. Observe other members talking and reflect on how he/she sold the items and received payment from colleagues.

Active Experimentation (AC): Any member of the group who could not perform the tasks outlined at the CE stage would be asked to perform them after following what others did in the first three stages. The member would:

- i. Download three online stores' application on his/her smart phones e.g. Jumia, Konga and Kaymu or visit the websites of the three online stores.
- ii. Navigate through each of the online store's application and define what they offer to the public.
- iii. Purchase an educational item(s) not more than N2,000 from any of the online stores after comparing the price, quality and ease of delivery.
- iv. Design an e-marketing advert to sell the educational item to your colleagues at affordable price.
- v. Collect the data of request for the items sent in by colleagues.
- vi. Sell to Colleagues who meet the conditions of sales ensuring they make payment directly using e-payment platform.

Note: where all members are able to perform excellently well at all the first three stages of CE, AC, and RO, the entire group members would be required to:

- i. Navigate the online stores for further learning and discussions.

**Conditions/Ethical
 Issues for using
 these
 learning**

- i. All students must have smart phones/laptops which can access the internet or download apps for browsing.
 - ii. Students must be willing to spend not less than N5,000 for the purpose of buying online and selling.
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activities:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> iii. Students must be willing to work in small team of five persons each. iv. Students must be matured at ages ranging from 16 years and above. v. Student must have a social media account with Facebook, WhatsApp or Instagram. vi. Two hours must be provided weekly for groups to meet and discussions based on the learning tasks must be given. vii. Four weeks must be provided for the entire learning activities.
Learning materials:	<p>The following learning materials are required of every student who will participate in carrying out these experiential learning activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Pen ii. Note book or Jotter iii. N5000 in a dedicated bank account.
Learning tools:	<p>The following learning tools are required of every student who will participate in the experiential learning activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Smart phone with camera/laptop with internet connectivity. ii. Play Store for downloaded online stores app iii. Graphic apps for designing e-marketing adverts.
Learning environments:	<p>For the purpose of these learning activities, the learning environment are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Online environment. ii. Physical classroom for class discussions. iii. The real world for picking and distributing items bought and sold online. iv. Entrepreneurship guidance for further group interactions
Teacher's activity:	<p>The teacher is to carry out the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Organise students in smaller groups of five persons each. ii. Provide each group with the learning activities to be carried out at each stage. iii. Monitor groups' discussions during meeting hours. iv. Receive complaints and address them immediately to ensure harmony within group. v. Design instruments for assessing students' e-business competencies and for assessing knowledge development. vi. Assess the students at the end of the forth week for examination purpose.
Formative assessment:	<p>At end of the forth week, each student would be required to fill self-evaluation form on the abilities he/she has developed through the experiential learning activities. Abilities to be assessed are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. ability to search for products and prices online using applications such as Konga, Jumia and Kaymu; ii. ability to compare prices online, iii. ability to place online order, iv. ability to track order online, v. ability to make online payment, vi. ability to design online advert, vii. ability to sell online, and viii. ability to track customers' order online.
Summative assessment:	<p>The teacher is to assess the students by administering a test based on the learning objectives testing knowledge comprehension or development covering the following questions:</p>

- i. Define what online stores do.
 - ii. State the technologies needed for navigating online stores.
 - iii. State the knowledge needed for buying from online stores.
 - iv. State the skills needed for navigating an online store.
 - v. Explain the procedures of buying from an online store.
 - vi. Explain the logistics associated with online buying.
 - vii. State the challenges associated with buying and selling using electronic digital technology.
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Source: Abdulkarim and Ordu, 2018.

It is worth noting that there is no empirical evidence yet to support utilization of this instructional design as proposed by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018). This is despite the claims made by the authors that e-business competencies related to online business transactions and e-payment can be developed by students through one-shot learning activities. Therefore, if this instructional design must be embraced by educators especially those saddled with the responsibility of teaching marketing and other e-business concepts, there is need to empirically test the effect the design on students' development of e-business competencies as proposed by authors. Thus, the need for this present study cannot be emphasised. However, in this study, the e-business competencies to be assessed include those assessed by Oborah (2014) such as: ability to add to wish list, and add or drop from the cart.

1.1 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to test the effect of experiential instructional design proposed by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) on Business education students' e-business competencies development in Rivers State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- 1) Determine whether Business education students' develop e-business competencies after being exposed to e-business experiential instructional design learning activities as outlined by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018).
- 2) Determine the e-business competence ability level of Business education students after being exposed to e-business experiential instructional design learning activities as outlined by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018).

1.2 Research Questions

- 1) What are the e-business competencies developed by Business education students after being exposed to e-business experiential instructional design learning activities outlined by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018)?
- 2) What are the ability levels of Business education students in performing e-business tasks after being exposed to experiential instructional design learning activities outlined by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018)?

1.3 Hypothesis

Ho₁: Experiential instructional learning activities as proposed by Abdulkarim and Pac (2018) have no significant influence on Business education students' development of e-business competencies.

2. Methods

This study adopts quasi-experimental research design with post-test, non-randomized groups. The population and sample of the study consists of 22 NCE I Business education students during the 2018/2019 academic session who were to study commerce BED 113 and BED 123. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the participants for the study based on the following criteria: (1) that the participants are in NCE I, and (2) that the participants have passed commerce course (BED 113). This sampling technique was deemed appropriate because of the use of intact classes and criteria for pre-qualification to be part of the participants.

A participant self-evaluation questionnaire tagged: Participants; Responses on E-Business Competencies Developed after Experiential Instructional Design Learning Activities Questionnaire (PREBUCDAEIDLAQ) was designed by the research for data collection. The questionnaire contained 20 items, 10 to each of the research question. The responses to the items of the questionnaire were structured based on four rating scales of Highly Developed (3-points), Developed (2-points) and Not Developed (1-point) for items relating to research question 1 and High Ability (HA – 3 points), Moderate Ability (MA – 2points) and Low Ability (1-point).

The instruments were subjected to face validity by an expert in Educational Measurement and Evaluation in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University and one lecturer of Business education from Federal College of Education (Tech.), Omoku – Rivers State. The reliability of internal consistency for instrument was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha to obtain a reliability index of 0.72.

2.1 Model Specification

A substituted Simple Linear Regression Model (SLRM) was used as a model for this study. The substituted proposed model is given as:

Students' E-Business Competencies Development = f (Students' Ability Level in Performing E-business tasks)

Explicitly, the model is written as:

$$SECD = a + \beta SALPET$$

Where:

SECD = Students' E-Business Competencies Development

SALPET = Students' Ability Level in Performing E-business Tasks

a = constant

Hence, experiential instructional design learning activities is proxy by students' ability level in performing e-business tasks.

The proposed model is represented diagrammatical as:

Figure 1: Experiential instructional design Learning activities model
(Source: Researcher, 2019)

3. Research Procedures

One of the researchers who doubled also as the course lecturer for commerce (BED123) during the 2018/2019 academic session, asked the students to undertake the learning activities proposed by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) for the purpose of learning practical e-commerce. The students were required to complete the learning activities six weeks into the semester while attending class for other instructions. The students were asked to turn-in their progress report on weekly basis for the purpose of monitoring their progress. At end of the fourth week, each student was to come to class with evidence of delivery of the product bought with not more than N3,000 from Jumia and sell to other students who have indicated interest through their social media designed adverts. At the end of the sixth week, students were given the self-evaluation questionnaire to fill in the class before the day's lecture. The data were collated and analysed using mean and simple linear regression with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. For decision making purpose, the following were used as guide:

- a) Mean of 2.0 and above will be regarded as High Developed (VD) or High Ability (HA), 1.5 to 1.99 will be regarded as Developed (D) or Moderate Ability (MA), and below 1.5 will be regarded as Not Developed (ND) or Low Ability (LA).
- b) In testing the null hypotheses, the decision rule of computation with SPSS will be used to draw conclusion regarding the results obtained.

4. Results and Discussions

Research question 1: What are the e-business competencies developed by Business education students after being exposed to e-business experiential instructional design learning activities outlined by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018)?

Table 1: Mean Scores of Business Education Students' Ability Level
in Performing E-business Tasks

N/S	Items	HA	MA	LA	Mean	Decision
1	searching for products online	27	26	0	2.41	HA
2	comparing prices online	21	30	0	2.32	HA
3	placing online order	36	18	01	2.50	HA
4	tracking order online	18	30	01	2.23	HA
5	making online payment	36	20	01	2.55	HA
6	designing advert for social media	27	26	0	2.41	HA
7	negotiating sales through social media	27	26	0	2.41	HA
8	tracking customers' order online	30	24	0	2.45	HA
9	adding to wish list	36	24	0	2.55	HA
10.	adding or dropping from the cart	24	28	0	2.36	HA
Cluster mean					2.42	HA

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

The result in Table 1 shows that Business education students exposed to experiential instructional design learning activities are of the opinion that they developed high ability in performing the specific e-business tasks relating searching for products online, comparing prices online, placing online order, tracking order online, making online payment, designing advert for social media, negotiating sales through social media, tracking request, adding to wish list and adding or dropping form the cart with mean of 2.23, 2.32, 2.36, 2.41, 2.45, 2.50, and 2.55 respectively for item 1 to 10. The cluster means score of 2.42 also shows that students developed high ability in performing the e-business tasks given through experiential instructional design.

Research question 2: What are the ability levels of Business education students in performing e-business tasks after being exposed to experiential instructional design learning activities outlined by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018)?

Table 2: Mean Scores of Students' e-Business Competencies Developed

N/S	Items	HD	D	ND	Mean	Decision
11	ability to search for products online using Jumia	48	12	0	2.73	HD
12	ability to compare prices online	42	16	0	2.64	HD
13	ability to place online order	51	10	0	2.77	HD
14	ability to track order online	33	20	01	2.45	HD
15	ability to make online payment	51	10	0	2.77	HD
16	ability to design advert for social media	42	16	0	2.64	HD
17	ability to negotiate sales through social media	48	12	0	2.73	HD

18	ability to track customers' order online	51	10	0	2.77	HD
19	ability to add to wish list	57	06	0	2.86	HD
20.	add or drop from the cart	48	12	0	2.73	HD
Cluster mean					2.71	HD

Source: Field Work, 2019.

The result in Table 2 shows that Business education students exposed to experiential instructional design learning activities highly developed e-business competencies relating to accessing online market platform (Jumia), placing order, tracking order, making online payment, designing advert for social media, negotiating sales through social media, tracking request, adding to wish list and adding or dropping form the cart with mean of 2.45, 2.64, 2.73, 2.77, and 2.86 respectively for item 11 to 20. The cluster means score 2.71 also shows that they highly developed the evaluated e-business competencies.

Hypothesis 1: Experiential instructional learning activities as proposed by Abdulkarim and Pac (2018) have no significant influence on Business education students' development of e-business competencies.

Table 3: Summary of Multiple Regression Model on the Impact of ICEEE model on Business Education Graduates' Jobs Creation in Omoku 2017 to 2019

Model R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
				R Square Change	F Change	df1df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.72 ^a	.52	.495	3.28	.52	21.60	1 20	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), VAR00002

Source: Field Work, 2019

Table 3 above shows linear regression (R) of 0.72, regression square of (R²) of 0.52, adjusted R² of 0.495, the standard error estimate is 3.28. The change statistics show R² 0.52 which means that all predictors that actually contributed significantly to the prediction, accounts for 52% of the variance in the Business education students e-business competencies development. Therefore, since the p value of 0.0001 is less than the assumed p value of 0.05, using SPSS, the null hypothesis was rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted. This means that experiential instructional design learning activities has significant influence on Business education students' development of e-business competencies.

5. Discussion of Findings

The results related to research question 1 show that Business education students developed high ability in performing the e-business tasks given through experiential instructional design. This is due to the fact that students were of the opinion that they developed high ability in performing the specific e-business tasks relating searching for

products online, comparing prices online, placing online order, tracking order online, making online payment, designing advert for social media, negotiating sales through social media, tracking request, adding to wish list and adding or dropping form the cart. These findings address the need noted by Oborah (2014) that Business students should develop fundamental e-commerce competencies in order to function effectively and efficiently in the entry-level employment in the e-commerce industry.

The results related to research question 2 show that Business education students highly developed the evaluated e-business competencies after exposed to experiential instructional design learning activities. This is because the students are of the opinion that they highly developed e-business competencies relating to accessing online market platform (Jumia), placing order, tracking order, making online payment, designing advert for social media, negotiating sales through social media, tracking request, adding to wish list and adding or dropping form the cart. These findings also justify the claims made by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) who believed the use of experiential instructional design would enable business education students to develop e-business competencies related to online business transactions and e-payment can be developed by students through one-shot learning activities.

The results of the test of hypothesis related to the two research questions show that experiential instructional design learning activities significantly influence Business education students' development of e-business competencies. This finding is driven by the fact that the students developed high ability in performing e-business tasks of the experiential instructional design learning activities and consequently highly developed e-business competencies.

5.1 Educational implication of the findings

Since the findings show that experiential instructional design learning activities assisted Business education students to highly develop e-business competencies, Business educators who want to bridge the gap between knowledge based competencies and skills competencies in this era of technological advances Ordu (2018) need to embrace the use of experiential instructional design to drive home their goals. However, to do this, they need to be retrained on experiential instructional design through a train-the-trainer workshop or they can equipped themselves with the knowledge of constructing instruction using experiential design by adopting the work of Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) and other related works.

6. Conclusions

It can be concluded from the findings of this study that experiential instructional design for e-business competencies development as proposed by Abdulkarim and Pac (2018) is a veritable tool in assisting Business education students to develop e-business competencies. This is because the students developed high ability level in performing the e-business tasks suggested by these authors and in turn highly developed e-business competencies related to accessing online market platform (Jumia), placing

order, tracking order, making online payment, designing advert for social media, negotiating sales through social media, tracking request, adding to wish list and adding or dropping form the cart at one or all of the 4-stages of learning activities. Hence, to assist Business education students develop e-business knowledge and skills through one-shot instruction, Business educators and other similar educators need to adopt and redesign the experiential instructional design proposed by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) to suit their own context.

6.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the educational implications and the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were put forward:

- 1) Business educators who want to bridge the gap between knowledge competency development and skills competency development should adopt experiential instructional design as proposed by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018).
- 2) Staff development and training sponsorship institutions such as: Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) should be approached to provide funding for train-the-trainer workshop on how to design and implement experiential instructional design in Business education and other related courses.
- 3) Business educators should utilize experiential instructional design as proposed by Abdulkarim and Ordu (2018) to enable their students make optimum use of their smart phones for learning and skills development purposes, hence changing the culture of using the phone only for social interaction.

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